

1 SIVmac239 infection in Rhesus Macaque and Sooty Mangabey.

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6 We studied HIV infection in a non-human primate model. We measured total gene expression by
7 microarray in normal tissues and in the tissues of primates of two species, the Rhesus Macaque and the
8 Sooty Mangabey to describe HIV infection in a systems biologic fashion *in vivo*. At 14 days post infection,
9 in the lymph nodes monkeys displayed activation of killer cell signaling (NKG7), cytotoxic and helper T
10 resources (e.g., GNLY, GZMB and TBX21), and cells were proliferative even in the secondary lymphoid
11 organs (e.g., MKI67). The lymph nodes of infected monkeys produced *CCL3*. We describe here activation
12 of *DDX10* in primates following SIV infection *in vivo*.

13 Citations

14 1. Martins, M.A., Bischof, G.F., Shin, Y.C., Lauer, W.A., Gonzalez-Nieto, L., Watkins, D.I., Rakasz,
15 E.G., Lifson, J.D. and Desrosiers, R.C., 2019. Vaccine protection against SIVmac239 acquisition.
16 Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 116(5), pp.1739-1744.

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